

Community building for FAIR data

Connie Clare, PhD
Community Manager
c.e.clare@tudelft.nl
[@ConnieEClare](https://twitter.com/ConnieEClare)

28th September 2021

*UK Conference of Bioinformatics and Computational Biology
(UKCBCB 2021) DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.5526034](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5526034)*

Questions to be answered...

- What is 4TU.ResearchData?
- Why do we need community?
- Who are our community members?
- What is our goal?
- What do we do together?

What is 4TU.ResearchData?

- International data repository
<https://data.4tu.nl/portal>
- Available to researchers globally
- Founded in 2010

UNIVERSITY
OF TWENTE.

4TU.Federation

Science

Engineering

Design

Sharing

Curation

Access

Preservation

8,000+
datasets

Tailored discipline-specific solutions for FAIR data

- Atmospheric science (3321 datasets)
- Geomatic engineering (3213 datasets)
- Climate change (3211 datasets)

Technical infrastructure AND... **human infrastructure!**

Why do we need community?

Good infrastructure on its own won't make data FAIR. We need to work with and invest in **people**.

Research communities and disciplinary problems cross institutional borders. We should collaborate in solving them.

UNIVERSITY
OF TWENTE.

4TU.Federation

WAGENINGEN
UNIVERSITY & RESEARCH

What do we mean by 'community'?

Community is when...

- People with a **shared purpose** come together to **achieve goals** and **tasks** they wouldn't be able to on their own.
- **Information flows** in multiple directions.
- Provides **opportunities** for **learning**.
- Members foster **meaningful connections** and feel a sense of **belonging** and **inclusivity**.

Definition adapted from the [CSCCE.org](https://www.cscce.org)

Image by [eko pramono](#) from [Pixabay](#)

Who are our community members?

<https://community.data.4tu.nl/>

What is goal of our community?

Our community aims to provide an inclusive space for researchers and data supporters to connect and exchange knowledge about the best practices for creating and reusing FAIR data.

What do we do together and how?

Engagement and education

- Working & focus groups
- Training, workshops, demos

Reward and recognition

- Researcher/data support stories
- Celebrating data initiatives

FAIR data incentives

- FAIR Data Funds
- Fellowship program

Monthly working groups

Google Docs

- Established January 2021
- 15 to 18 data stewards
- 1 hour (+ work in between as required)
- Share experiences & ask questions
- Learn from one another & gain confidence
- Contribute ideas and co-create resources
- FAIR and reproducible code
- Privacy and GDPR
- Engagement and education

FAIR and reproducible code working group

Aim(s): Data stewards learn about tools and environments; writing, documenting and testing code; version control and collaboration; pipelines for programming languages; and, archiving and licensing of software code.

Deliverable:

- ‘Train the trainer’ workshop: ‘Writing FAIR and Reproducible code’ on 24 & 25 June (5 instructors, 12 learners). [Read the blog!](#)

Privacy and GDPR working group

Aims(s): Data stewards learn how to advise researchers about appropriate management of personal and/or commercially sensitive data (informed consent, legal/ethics).

Deliverable:

- Published set of guidelines about data agreements (DPAs, DTAs, Joint controllership, NDAs)

Engagement and education working group

You're an Organizer

ENGAGEMENT AND
EDUCATION WORKING
GROUP

Private / Group

+13 members

Aim(s): Data stewards share experiences about their role and develop workflows to support researchers with data management.

Deliverable(s):

- Inventory of generic and disciplinary RDM training provided by 4TU institutions.
- Published set of use cases demonstrating discipline-specific practices, and RDM challenges and solutions.

‘PYTHON ESSENTIALS FOR
GIS LEARNERS’: A
TARGETED FAIR RESEARCH
WORKSHOP BY TU
DELFT’S DIGITAL
COMPETENCE CENTRE

Are you interested in learning
to program with Python? Are
you currently working with
data using geographic

Training and workshops

- The Carpentries (2018)
- Software & Data
- 4x half-days (TUD, TU/e, UT, Leiden)
- Massive Open Online Course on Open Science
- 4-week introductory course
- Researchers and support staff
- Essentials 4 Data Support (RDNL)
- Data support professionals
- Disciplinary courses (by DCC)
- Success stories & lessons learned

- Nadia Bloemendaal
- RDNL Dutch data prize winner
- Paper in Nature
- View, downloads & citations

<https://community.data.4tu.nl/members/nadiabloemendaal/>

<https://doi.org/10.4121/12706085.v3>

<https://community.data.4tu.nl/2021/01/20/tropical-cyclone-risk-research-taking-the-world-by-storm/>

ST

Vers

(Har

Data

Trop

Glot

usin

calci

VER

in th

VER

track

HIST

2

3

1

PUB

TROPICAL CYCLONE RISK RESEARCH: TAKING THE WORLD BY STORM

Connie Clare
January 20, 2021

0 Comments

Nadia Bloemendaal tells the story behind her *RDNL Dutch Data Prize* winning 'STORM' dataset that has been downloaded more than 3,600 times since its publication in *4TU.ResearchData*.

Nadia Bloemendaal is a PhD researcher at the *Institute of Environmental Studies (IVM)* at *Vrije Universiteit (VU)* in Amsterdam. Her research investigates tropical cyclone risk and how this is impacted by climate change.

Nadia's childhood dream to study extreme weather began when she was just eight years old after watching the 1996 American epic disaster film, 'Twister'.

DS

71
downloads

5
citations

peer-reviewed publication

a global synthetic tropical
dataset using STORM

Data

Sciences
rds
Climate Change

Best Track Archive fo...

Community news...

UPDATE ON DEVELOPER POSITION AT 4TU.RESEARCHDATA

 Ardi Nonhebel
April 12, 2021

 0 Comments

The vacancy for the [Developer of Open Science Data Infrastructures](#) closed last week. We have received 21 applications.

Our timeline for progressing with these applications is:

- Shortlisting: w/c 19 April
- First round of interviews: w/c 26 April
- Second round of interviews: w/c 10 May

Written by [Ardi Nonhebel](#) and [Marta Teperek](#)

Reward and recognition

- Recognition of service
- New community initiatives
- Cross-institutional collaborations
- Repository features
- Vacancies and opportunities

Celebrating data: Your daily dose

4TU.ResearchData
@4TUResearchData

Your daily dose!

NEW #Data from @TUeindhoven's @bmttue #researcher @Fluo_renzo et al.

Formulation of tunable size PLGA-PEG #nanoparticles for #drugdelivery using #microfluidic #technology

#Dataset doi.org/10.4121/145723...
(CC BY-ND-NC)

#Biomedicalengineering

9:30 AM · Jun 2, 2021 · Twitter Web App

4TU.ResearchData
@4TUResearchData

Your daily dose!

NEW #Data collection by Giordano Lipari @hydrodynamics @sph_delft

High-resolution SPH #simulations of a 2D dam-break flow against a vertical wall

5 datasets doi.org/10.4121/c.5353...

#civil #maritime #engineering
#smoothedparticlehydrodynamics #FAIR

9:00 am · 12 May 2021 · Twitter Web App

2 Retweets 2 Likes

4TU.ResearchData
@4TUResearchData

Your daily dose!

NEW #Soilscience #data by P. Zhang et al. @FacultyITC @UTwente

10-year surface soil moisture #dataset produced based on in situ measurements collected from the Tibetan Plateau observatory.

Dataset doi.org/10.4121/127637...

#geology #TibetObs #FAIRdata

9:30 am · 19 May 2021 · Twitter Web App

2 Retweets 2 Likes

Your daily dose!

NEW #Data from @UTwente #PhD student Luca Marotta on...

😊 Physical fatigue detection after running around an athletic track!

👉 If you're interested in #Biomedical #Engineering, #Human #Movement & #Sports #Science, check out bit.ly/fatiguedetecti...

6:38 am · 1 Apr 2021 · Twitter Web App

3 Retweets 3 Likes

Reward and recognition

Dataset underlying the research on physical fatigue detection in running using inertial measurement units (IMUs)

**UNIVERSITY
OF TWENTE.**

<https://doi.org/10.4121/14307743>

Did you see these datasets? (Monthly round-up)

Did you see these datasets?

Last month's top downloaded datasets in the 4TU ResearchData repository!

SandT-Pro: Sand Transport Process measurements under Breaking and Irregular Waves

Author(s): Joep van der Zander, Jan Ribberink, Tom O'Donoghue, Dominic van der A, David Hurther, Peter Thorne and Iván Cáceres

Institution: [University of Twente](#)

Categories: [Geology](#), [Physical Geography and Environmental Geoscience](#)

Keywords: 000 Computer science, knowledge & systems, Business Process Intelligence (BPI), IEEE Task Force on Process Mining, real life event logs

[View the dataset](#)

BPI Challenge 2012

Author(s): Boudewijn van Dongen

Institution: [Eindhoven University of Technology](#)

Categories: [Information Systems](#), [Business and Management](#)

Keywords: 000 Computer science, knowledge & systems, Business Process Intelligence (BPI), IEEE Task Force on Process Mining, real life event log

[Read more](#) about Boudewijn's research and [view the dataset](#)

Inventory of RDM policy for a selection of academic publishers and journals in 2016

Author(s): Rutger de Jong, Henk van den Hoogen, Fieke Schoots, Mariëtte van Selm and [Madeleine de Smaele](#)

Institution: [Delft University of Technology](#), UKB Working Group Research Data

Categories: Library and Information Studies, Policy and Administration

Keywords: Data policies, Data repositories, Data sharing, Journal publishers, Research data

Inventory of RDM policy for a selection of academic publishers and journals in 2016

Cite Download (290.61 kB) Share Embed + Collect

Dataset posted on 19.02.2018, 00:00 by R.M. (Rutger) de Jong, H.J.M. (Henk) van den Hoogen, S.P. (Fieke) Schoots, [Mariëtte van Selm](#), [Madeleine de Smaele](#)

USAGE METRICS [↗](#)

265 views	2891 downloads	0 citations
-----------	----------------	-------------

This spreadsheet contains an inventory of data policies of publishers and journals. It has been

FAIR Data Funds

- Researchers from 4TU institutions
- 3.500 EUR budget per application
- Spring & Autumn call

<https://data.4tu.nl/info/en/use/data-funds>

- Metadata standards & documentation
- Anonymisation & aggregation
- Proprietary → open-source platform
- Visualisation & promotion

Meet the Spring Call grantees

- Claudiu Forgaci (Urban design)
- Frank Halfwerk (Biomedical)
- Michelle Kip (Health Technology)
- Ria Wolkorte (Health Technology)
- João Moreira (Cyber Security)
- Thomas Groen (Natural resources)
- Pavlo Bazilinsky (Cognitive robotics)

<https://community.data.4tu.nl/2021/05/15/fair-data-fund-spring-call-2021-meet-the-grantees/>

Internship programme

Coming soon...
Watch this space!

- Launching in 2022
- Global initiative
- Recruit & embed interns
- Champion FAIR data initiatives
- Advance mission & vision

- Learn more about Open Science
- Inform & drive new developments
- Learn & practice new skills
- Publications and conferences
- Boosts CV – career opportunities
in third space!

Thank you for your attention!

Quick links:

[Information website](#)

[Data portal](#)

[Community platform](#)

[Subscribe to mailing list](#)

[Highlights 2020](#)

Contact

c.e.clare@tudelft.nl

[@ConnieEClare](#)